

Exploring Herbal Telomerase Activators as Promising Interventions for Skin Aging

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Abstract

Advancing age is an unavoidable process that affects organs and systems, impacting life expectancy and healthy life in the population, and could lead to a variety of age-related diseases. One of the most prominent attributes of aging is skin aging which emerges as a complex phenomenon characterized by visible signs such as loss of elasticity, wrinkles, and age spots, which significantly impact overall appearance and well-being. Inflammaging, which is a chronic state of systemic inflammation associated with age-related diseases, directly affects the skin and accelerates the process of skin aging by impairing cellular functions. In this context, cellular senescence, immune dysregulation, and the accumulation of damaged molecules are recognized as key contributors to inflammaging. Of particular importance are telomeres, protective caps at the ends of chromosomes, which play a critical role in aging. Critically short telomeres can induce cellular senescence or death, contributing to age-related conditions.

Telomerase, an enzyme extending telomeres, becomes a target for its potential in promoting telomere lengthening and counteracting aging effects. Anti-aging research focuses on telomeres, with an emphasis on exploring herbal telomerase activators to extend telomeres naturally. Plant-based compounds offer promise due to their natural origin, minimizing risks associated with synthetic compounds. These activators may reduce oxidative stress, a contributor to aging, and influence signaling pathways related to aging and inflammation.

This article aims to provide a comprehensive review of plants exhibiting telomere lengthening characteristics on skin cells. The exploration of these natural components not only provides insights into the underlying mechanisms of aging but also offers potential strategies for promoting healthy aging and extending the youthful appearance of the skin.

Keywords: Aging, Cellular Senescence, Telomerase, Plant extracts.

Introduction

As life expectancy continues to increase, age-related diseases can impose significant financial and emotional burdens on society. Increased life expectancy has led to an increasing number of elderly people being at risk of age-related diseases. Age-related illnesses are currently the leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide[1]. Consequently, there is an urgent need to develop more conducive approaches for the prevention and treatment of age-related conditions, as well as slowing down the aging process[2].

Indeed, the majority of essential organs and tissues in the body experience a decline in function as they age. Consequently, bones lose mass and density, muscle strength deteriorates, the skin undergoes visible changes, and there may be indications of impaired wound healing.

Skin aging emerges as a prominent hallmark of the aging phenomenon. though not all the mechanisms behind skin aging

are fully understood, a few have been investigated to play a key role in the process. These mechanisms include oxidative stress, photoaging and Inflammation[3].

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are unstable molecules consisting of oxygen that readily interact with other molecules within a cell. Oxidative stress is characterized by an imbalance between antioxidant activity and intracellular oxidation, resulting in cells undergoing oxidation and generating a significant quantity ROS. Elevated levels of ROS not only accelerate the aging process of skin cells but also contribute to a decline in collagen levels within the skin tissue, resulting in wrinkle formation and skin relaxation[4]. In addition, excessive presence of ROS within cells leads to mitochondrial damage, diminished production of mitochondrial ATP, reduced mitochondrial membrane potential, and triggers a chain reaction that advances the aging process[5].

Skin photoaging refers to premature aging of the skin due to frequent exposure to ultraviolet radiation, resulting in a range of

histological and clinical changes[6]. Prolonged exposure to solar ultraviolet radiation results in photoaging, inducing fibroblasts and keratinocytes to release matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), which degrade components of the dermal extracellular matrix, such as collagen[7].

Among these mechanisms, inflammation stands out as a critical factor in skin aging. Aging is associated with a progressive increase in the level of basal systemic inflammation called inflammaging, which plays an important role in promoting age-related diseases[8]. One of the most important driving forces of inflammaging is senescence[9]. Senescence, which is defined as a cell cycle arrest in response to cellular stress and damage, contributes to an altered secretome produced by senescent cells known as senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP), resulting in an imbalance in favor of pro-inflammatory mediators over anti-inflammatory mediators which fuel inflammaging[10].

Senescent cells could be generated via various mechanisms among which telomere shortening is a key factor[11, 12] as telomeres are repetitive DNA segments that form caps at the end of the chromosomes to protect the genetic material of the cell and keep the DNA from being frayed [13]and are regularly shortened during cell division[14].

Telomere shortening can be replication-dependent or independent. In a replication-dependent manner, telomere shortening occurs due to the end replication problem, whereas in a replication-independent manner, oxidative stress predominantly damages DNA and results in telomere shortening. Telomere shortening can be reversed by telomerase, an enzyme that contributes to the reconstruction and extension of telomeres in chromosomes by adding base[15]. Aging has been shown to be associated with a decline in telomerase activity [16].

Regardless of the underlying reasons for senescence, the cell cycle has been arrested and SASP phenotype has been developed[17]. Since senescent cells through SASP could propagate inflammaging throughout the body, exploiting anti-inflammatory based phytochemicals which can target senescent cells in different ways have the potential to effectively suppress inflammaging.

Natural resources have always been a focus of pharmacological interest because of their safety profiles and diversity of bioactive compounds, mainly their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory characteristics, and their ability to counteract oxidative stress and inflammation. Recent studies have revealed that these naturally occurring antioxidative agents can be used to decrease the rate of telomere shortening, which can potentially ease and mitigate the negative effects of age-related disorders [18]. Therefore, they could be a rich repertoire of senotherapeutic phytochemicals for senotherapy of inflammaging.

Senotherapeutic phytochemicals can affect senescent cells in three ways: Senolytic, SASP suppressor, or senomorphic and inhibitor of senescent cell accumulation[19]. Several studies have been conducted in recent years, demonstrating that specific plant-based constituents can be used as senotherapeutic phytochemicals by inducing telomerase activity and reversing the process of telomere shortening, which results in senescence [20].

The major active constituents chosen for this study are polysaccharides, flavonoids, saponins, and polyphenols, which are phytochemicals with intricate chemical structures that appear to be capable of modulating or regulating telomerase activity[21]. Despite the lack of a complete understanding of how these compounds activate telomerase, research has indicated that they do so by neutralizing reactive oxidative stress (ROS) and modulating various signaling pathways[21].

This review discusses the effects of herbal extracts from *Rhodiola rosea*, *Astragalus membranaceus*, *Centella asiatica*, *Cistanche Genus*, *Panax ginseng*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Angelica sinensis*, *Spirulina platensis* and *Scutellaria baicalensis* as potential senotherapeutic phytochemical candidates by triggering telomerase activity in skin cells.

Rhodiola rosea

Rhodiola rosea, a member of the Crassulaceae family, has a long history of application as an adaptogenic compound. *Rhodiola rosea* is traditionally believed to stimulate non-specific immunity. Among the various compounds found in this plant, salidroside and rosavin stand out as its main bioactive components. Studies have revealed that Salidroside and rosavin have neuroprotective, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, and antioxidant effects[22].

Salidroside (2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) ethyl- β -D-glycopyranoside) phenylpropanoid glycoside and rosavin (cinnamyl mono- and diglycosides), which are more abundant in the rhizome of *Rhodiola rosea* than in the roots[23]. Salidroside is known for its significant neuroprotective, anti-fatigue, and anti-aging effects as well as its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-tumor, and anti-depression effects. study showed that both compounds have the potential to prevent telomere shortening in leukemia, fibroblasts, and keratinocytes. One study reported the preventive effects of salidroside (0.1% w/w) when orally administered to guinea pigs before UVB irradiation. This study revealed that salidroside effectively halted the thickening of the epidermis, suppressed UVB-induced apoptosis, and inhibited the formation of sunburn cells (SBC) within the epidermis.[24]. Another study evaluated the anti-aging effects of *R. rosea* extract using qualitative and quantitative methods. This included analyzing the immunofluorescence images and conducting a telomerase activity assay. Chromatography was used to isolate and measure the active ingredients. When exposed to UVA and UVB, cultured HaCaT cells underwent morphological changes associated with photoaging. However, treatment of cells with *R. rosea* extract, salidroside, and rosavin reversed the photoaging effects, resulting in increased telomerase activity and reduced cellular damage. Extracts with higher salidroside and rosavin content exhibited better preventive effects. These findings support *R. rosea*'s effectiveness as an anti-aging solution and suggest its integration into mainstream healthcare practices [25]. An in vitro study was conducted to investigate the anti-aging effect of a combination of *Undaria pinnatifida*, *Tribulus terrestris*, *Rhodiola rosea*, *Moringa oleifera*, folic acid, and vitamin B12 against photoaging in the skin. The tested mixture effectively prevented UV-induced morphological alterations in both fibroblasts and keratinocytes, while inhibiting proinflammatory and senescence-

related pathways[26]. The exact mechanism of solidoside and rosavin activation of telomerase has not been elucidated; however, a few mechanisms have been proposed for their action on telomerase. One mechanism is that solidoside and rosavin may activate the expression of the human telomerase reverse transcriptase gene, which is responsible for producing the

telomerase enzyme that directly affects telomere length. Another mechanism is that both compounds may protect against oxidative stress, which is a known cause of telomere shortening, and subsequently indirectly affects telomerase.

Figure1: telomere biology in cells and the effect of certain herbal extracts on telomere shortening.

Astragalus membranaceus

Astragalus membranaceus, a flowering plant in the family Fabaceae, is a traditional Chinese medicinal herb that has been investigated for its application as a potential anti-inflammatory agent in treating inflammation associated conditions[27].

Studies have demonstrated that *A. membranaceus* and its primary constituents, such as saponins, flavonoids, and polysaccharides, show promising effects on senescent cells [28]. Flavonoids have a wide range of pharmacological properties and are considered promising candidates for promoting overall health and longevity. Their pleiotropic effects directly or indirectly affect (Senescence-associated beta-galactosidase) activity, cellular lifespan, and other senescence markers. These effects include preserving SASP (Senescence-associated secretory phenotype), inducing apoptosis in senescent cells (SCs), and triggering diverse protective cellular mechanisms. Evidence from animal experiments indicates that the anti-senescence effects of flavonoids are predominantly senomorphic, with only a minority exhibiting senolytic effects. Although the exact mechanisms of action remain unclear, their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties have been proposed to be crucial, as they are the primary factors associated with senescence and senescence-associated diseases. *Astragalus* contains antioxidants that can neutralize harmful free radicals and reduce oxidative stress (ROS). By protecting cells from oxidative damage, *Astragalus* may indirectly support telomere maintenance. Chronic inflammation has also been associated with telomere shortening. Since *Astragalus* has anti-inflammatory properties, by reducing

inflammation, it may help protect telomeres from damage. In addition to their immunomodulatory and anticancer effects, these components have recently been reported to exert beneficial effects on telomeres by stimulating telomerase[29]. Cycloastragenol(CAG), a saponin extracted from *Astragalus* roots, promotes telomerase activity in human CD4 and CD8 T-cells [30]. CAG has been observed to activate telomerase mainly by modulating MAPK and Akt signaling pathways leading to the phosphorylation of telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) through post-transcriptional modification, thus promoting telomerase activity[31]. In another study, CAG supplementation in healthy subjects for 12 months resulted in increased telomere length [32]. A recent study revealed that the number of cells with short telomeres decreased in circulating lymphocytes from 18 healthy donors (range 32–86 years) after in vitro exposure to hydroethanolic root extract (HRE) of *Astragalus*, suggesting that the HRE [33] could be potentially used for the management of senescence-associated illnesses[34].

Since 2016, the FDA has deemed supplementary capsules containing *Astragalus* extracts as generally recognized as safe (GRAS) and available under the brand name TA65 [35]. A clinical trial spanning five years demonstrated that when paired with a vitamin supplement, TA-65 improved blood pressure, bone density, and metabolic markers in healthy individuals[36]. However, the trial did not assess the impact of TA-65 alone. In a separate study, TA-65 was found to enhance macular function in individuals with senescence-related macular degeneration[37]. Despite the promising cellular rejuvenation properties of such dietary supplements, it is essential to monitor their use through

licensed healthcare practitioners, as they may act as a potential carcinogen for individuals with a family history of cancer or those with higher cancer susceptibility [38].

The effects of an antiaging face cream with Astragaloside IV, a main component from the aqueous extract of *Astragalus membranaceus*, on telomere length in human skin samples were examined in a study with 20 participants [39]. After four weeks of daily application, the treatment group had a significantly higher average median telomere length than the control group, as well as improved skin brightness, elasticity and quality[40]. A separate clinical study showed that when ten healthy volunteers took a 250 mg oral capsule of *Astragalus* extract, their total arterial and carotid-radial arterial compliance improved

significantly after six months and an overall positive impact on vascular cell aging due to increase in telomerase activity was observed [41]. Another research study was carried out to examine the telomere length of 26 healthy individuals who had taken a dietary supplement containing polysaccharide extract of *Astragalus* (APS) and S-adenosyl-methionine (SAME). The findings revealed a significant difference in the telomere length of the individuals who had consumed the supplement in comparison to those who had not, despite being of similar age [42]. According to a clinical study done by Fernandez et al, Telomerase activator 65 was observed to improve crucial markers of cardiovascular disease risk, while simultaneously decreasing inflammation levels [43].

Figure2: The active phytochemical found in *Astragalus* plant and its potential as an edible supplementary capsule for activating human telomerase and providing anti-aging advantages

Centella asiatica

Centella asiatica, a herb belonging to the Apiaceae family, is a widely used traditional medicinal plant in Chinese medicine, which has been shown to be especially effective for improving cognitive ability, increasing antioxidant response and as a neuroprotective agent[44]. Therapeutic substances in *C. asiatica* are saponin-containing triterpene acids and their sugar esters, of which medecassic and asiatic acid are considered to be the most significant role in wound healing and anti-inflammation[45]. Its anti-senescence benefits have been investigated in recent studies[46]. In a particular investigation, continuous supplementation of 0.5 mg/mL resveratrol and two doses of DLBS1649 (25 and 50 µg/mL), which is a bioactive extract from *C. asiatica*, was studied for 15 weeks. The results demonstrated the ability of this supplementation to prevent telomere shortening and maintain telomerase activity in the *D. melanogaster* model compared to the control group [47]. Importantly, the administration of DLBS1649 did not significantly increase TP53 expression, indicating that it can serve as an anti-senescence agent without any risk of tumorigenicity. In another study, the

formulation 08AGT1, which includes *Centella asiatica* extract, was found to trigger an almost 9-fold increase in telomerase activity in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) compared with untreated cells[30]. In a 2019 study, the antioxidant effects of *C. asiatica* ethanol extract, along with other plant extracts, were evaluated on HaCaT cells (human keratinocytes). The increase in antioxidant activity was demonstrated primarily through inhibition of collagenase, with the ethanolic extract (CAE) demonstrating a 77.4% inhibition of collagenase[48]. Another study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of an anti-aging cream formulation containing *C. asiatica* and *Hypericum perforatum* on human skin cells. The combination of the two plant extracts resulted in a higher level of collagen 1A, which is an indicator of skin flexibility and durability[49]. In addition to its antioxidant activity, *C. asiatica* has been shown to have potential for scar prevention, wound healing, and fibroblast senescence[50]. It has been demonstrated that the extract derived from the plant effectively reduces wrinkles and possesses advantageous moisturizing properties[51]. Another study showed that a purified extract derived from *Centella asiatica*, containing polyphenolics and

triterpenes, can mitigate skin damage caused by inflammaging through reducing the production of IL-1 β , a cytokine associated with pro-inflammaging effects[52].

Several mechanisms have been proposed for the antioxidant and anti-senescence activities of Centella extract. Centella extracts, administered prior to exposure to H₂O₂, shielded dermal fibroblasts from cytotoxicity by enhancing cellular antioxidant processes. Callus extract (CE) supplementation increased CAT, GPx1, and SOD1 expression, while authentic plant extract (APE) pre-treatment induced SOD2 expression in response to H₂O₂. Additionally, CE and APE pre-treatment counteracted H₂O₂-

induced MMP-9 upregulation [53]. Notably, administering *Centella asiatica* supplement (reverse™) for three months restored TerT expression in middle-aged rats' brains[54]. Oxidative stress arises from ROS accumulation due to an imbalance between ROS production and antioxidant defense mechanisms. MMP-9, a zinc-containing gelatinase crucial for dermal extracellular matrix degradation, particularly collagen type IV, can be induced in skin cells by environmental factors such as UV exposure, tobacco smoke, and pollutants. Thus, substances with MMP-9 inhibitory properties hold promise for addressing skin aging [55].

Figure3: phytochemicals within specific plant extracts for targeting senescent cells caused by inflammation and oxidative stress and their effects on skin cell health restoration

Cistanche Genus

Plants of the Cistanche genus, known as desert hyacinths, are rich in glycosides and polysaccharides and have long been used in traditional herbal medicine for their anti-inflammatory properties [56]. In a mouse model of aging, Cistanche deserticola polysaccharides dosed at 25 mg/kg for six weeks were found to enhance telomerase activity in the heart and brain tissue [57]. Acteosides from Cistanche tubulosa, also applied in a mouse model of aging, were also found to increase telomerase activity in the heart and brain tissue when administered at a dose of 40 mg/kg for two weeks [57]. The mechanisms underlying these effects are not fully understood; however, C. deserticola has been shown to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects[58]. A recent investigation examined the anti-aging efficacy of a specific blend of four polyphenolic extracts (pomegranate, sweet orange, Cistanche, and Centella asiatica), which resulted in a significantly

reduced telomere shortening rate in replicating human dermal fibroblasts[59].

Experimental studies on mouse models have indicated that capsules containing cistanche herba can increase dermis thickness, elastic and collagen fiber content in the skin while maintaining telomere integrity. Moreover, the plant demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties by reducing the levels of plasma interleukin 1 β (IL-1 β) and matrix metalloproteinase 9 while increasing the level of IL-10. As a result, it effectively reduces systemic inflammation in the body.[60].

In a 12-week randomized clinical trial involving 60 female individuals of Caucasian descent exhibiting visible indications of photoaging, the consumption of a dietary supplement containing a botanical blend, including phenolic compounds derived from *Centella asiatica*, resulted in reductions in wrinkle depth and skin

roughness as well as improvements in skin elasticity, firmness, and radiance[61]. Clinical trials particularly investigating the impacts of Cistanche extracts on human telomere function are yet to be conducted.

Research has shown that Cistanche deserticola polysaccharide (CDPS) possesses notable anti-aging properties, primarily attributed to its antioxidative, anti-fatigue, memory-enhancing, and telomerase-boosting effects[62]. In a study by Zeng et al., the immunomodulatory impact of CDPS on mouse T cells was investigated[63]. CDPS not only increased the proliferation of mouse spleen and thymus lymphocytes independently but also promoted the proliferation of mouse thymus lymphocytes in

conjunction with ConA and PHA. Furthermore, this polysaccharide significantly elevated interleukin 2 secretion by lymphocytes, suggesting that CDPS's ability to enhance IL-2 secretion may be one of the mechanisms underlying Cistanche deserticola's immune-boosting and anti-aging effects. In another study by Yuan et al., the effects of CDPS on a D-galactose aging mouse model were examined[64]. The results demonstrated that CDPS effectively reduced malondialdehyde levels in tissues, increased telomerase activity in the heart and brain tissues, enhanced lymphocyte proliferation, and improved macrophage phagocytosis. These findings suggest that CDPS holds promise in counteracting free radical damage, enhancing telomerase activity, improving immune function, and retarding the aging process.

Table1: Brief summary of some herbal extracts with telomerase activating potential and their mechanism of action

Plant name	Family name	Active ingredient/s ource	Experimental model	efficacy	Possible mechanism	Ref.
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i>	Crassulaceae	Salidroside Rosavin	leukemia, fibroblasts, and keratinocytes	neuroprotective, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, and antioxidant prevent telomere shortening	may activate the expression of the human telomerase reverse transcriptase gene, protect against oxidative stress	[65]
			rats exposed to chronic stress	telomerase activation		
<i>Astragalus membranaceus</i>	Fabaceae	Saponin Flavonoid Polysaccharide Cycloastragenol	human CD4 and CD8 T-cells	Promotion of telomerase activity, reduced the effects of aging	modulating MAPK and PKB signaling pathways phosphorylation of (TERT) through post-transcriptional modification, reduce (ROS)	[30]
			Healthy human subjects	Increase in telomere length		[66]
				Decrease in the number of circulating lymphocytes with short telomeres		[33]
				Improvement in blood pressure, bone density, and metabolic markers		[66]
				Enhance in macular function		[67]
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Saponins mainly madecassic acid, asiatic acid	<i>D. melanogaster</i>	prevent telomere shortening	upregulating the cellular antioxidant machinery, upregulated CAT, GPx1, and SOD1 expression,	[47]
			human PBMC	increase in telomerase activity		[30]
			middle-aged rats	TERT expression in the brains was restored		[68]
<i>Cistanche</i> genus	Orobanchaceae	Acteosides	human dermal fibroblasts	reduced telomere shortening	anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects	[59]
			Aging mice	enhance telomerase activity in the heart and brain		[69]
<i>Panax ginseng</i>	Araliaceae	Ginsenoside (saponin)	<i>C. elegans</i>	increase in telomerase expression	unknown	[70]
			hematopoietic mice	increase telomerase activity	unknown	[71]
			senescent mice	increase telomerase activity	by increasing Lin28a, GDF-11, and SIRT1 expression	[72]
			Keratinocytes	upregulated the telomerase reverse transcriptase gene	unknown	[73]

<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Alkaloids, vitamin C, tannins, flavonoids, and phenolic	Human PBMCs	immunoregulatory, antioxidant, and anticancer increase in telomerase activity	unknown	[74]
<i>Angelica sinensis</i>	Apiaceae	polysaccharides	HSC in aging mice	antioxidant, neuroprotective, and immunomodulatory, increased telomerase and telomere length	unknown	[75]
<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	Oscillatoriaceae	Sapogenins	MCF7 cell lines	Increase in telomerase activity	unknown	[76]
<i>Scutellaria baicalensis</i>	Lamiaceae	Baicalin, Baicalein	UV-induced human dermal fibroblasts	Increase telomerase activity Decrease oxidative stress	Counteract REV-ERB α Increase BMAL1 expression increase MDA and MMP-1	[77]

CD4,CD8: cluster of differentiation; MAPK: Mitogen-activated protein kinases; PKB: Protein kinase B; TERT: telomerase reverse transcriptase; ROS: reactive oxygen species; PBMC: peripheral blood mononuclear cells; CAT: catalase; GPx1:Glutathione peroxidase 1; SOD1:superoxide dismutase type 1; HSC: hematopoietic stem cell; Lin28a:lin-28 homolog A; GDF-11:growth differentiation factor 11; SIRT1:sirtuin 1; MCF7: Michigan Cancer Foundation-7

Panax ginseng

P. ginseng is a perennial plant that grows in East Asian mountains. Ginseng phytochemicals, known as ginsenosides, are a group of triterpene saponins extracted from the roots of plants, and are considered some of the major medicinal constituents of ginseng[78]. Ginsenoside Rg1 was found to increase telomerase expression, thereby extending the lifespan of a nematode model (29).Rg1 has also been found to reduce the number of cells entering the G1 phase, decrease telomere shortening, and increase telomerase activity in hematopoietic mice[79].

A different study demonstrated that when ultraviolet-induced human fibroblasts were treated with ginsenoside Rg1, an increase in telomerase activity was observed. This increase in telomerase activity resulted in the inhibition of telomere shortening and delayed the onset of cellular senescence. The underlying mechanism of action involves the regulation of SIRT6 and NF- κ B pathways, along with a reduction in the expression of p21[80].

A research study investigated the anti-aging effects of Bazhen Decoction, a Chinese herbal formula containing ginseng, on progeroid mouse embryo fibroblasts (MEFs). The findings indicated that Bazhen Decoction enhanced the expression of DNA helicases, which facilitated the elongation of telomeres and DNA replication, thereby helping rescue the cells from senescence[81].

Korean red ginseng (KRG) demonstrated an in vivo effect against senescence by suppressing senescence-linked thymic involution without remarkable cytotoxicity[82]. This KRG-mediated anti-senescence effect was achieved by increasing Lin28a, GDF-11, and SIRT1 expression, along with an increase in the number of regulatory T cells in the spleen and natural killer (NK) cells expressing IFN- γ in aged mice. These findings suggest that KRG counteracts senescence by regulating the expression of senescence-associated genes and the composition of immune cell

subsets in aged mice. In conclusion, the results indicate that KRG counteracts senescence by regulating the expression of senescence-associated genes and the population of specific immune cell subsets in senescent mice. Another study revealed that KRG (100 and 200 μ g/mL) treatment of keratinocytes upregulated the telomerase reverse transcriptase gene, a catalytic subunit of telomerase [73]. An alternative study has demonstrated that the supplementation of ginseng oligopeptides in senescent mice embryonic fibroblasts delays oxidative stress, leading to enhanced telomerase activity and cell viability [83].

Angelica sinensis

Angelica sinensis, commonly known as dong quai, has been extensively used as a nourishing agent in traditional Chinese medicine for the treatment of gynecological diseases[84].Recent studies have shown that polysaccharides in *A. sinensis* are the main bioactive components with anti-inflammatory properties [85].In a mouse model of hematopoietic stem cell aging, Dong quai polysaccharide increased telomerase and telomere length, while reducing P53 protein[79]. Similarly, another study demonstrated that the polysaccharides derived from *Angelica sinensis* (ASP) and *Astragalus membranaceus* (AMP) possess anti-aging properties. These polysaccharides were found to regulate the p53-p21 and p16-pRb pathways and enhance telomerase activity in human fetal lung fibroblast WI-38 cells, preventing premature senescence induced by H2O2[86].

Phyllanthus emblica

Amalaki Rasayana , a drug prepared from the fruits of *Phyllanthus emblica* is popularly used in Indian traditional medicine to prevent or treat various age related health conditions such as hepatic and cardiac diseases[87]. Alkaloids, vitamin C, tannins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds present in this herb

possess immunoregulatory, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities[88]. Recently, researchers have focused on its potential as a telomere activator. In one study, the telomerase activity of healthy individuals aged (45–60) administered with amalaki for 90 days was analyzed in their blood samples, specifically in peripheral blood mononuclear cells[74]. The data were compared with those of the age-matched placebo group, and an increase in telomerase activity was observed.

Spirulina platensis

Spirulina platensis is a filamentous blue-green alga that is rich in vitamin minerals and proteins[89]. It is cultured worldwide as a superfood source and has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties[90]. In a recent study, the effects of sapogenins extracted from *Spirulina* on telomerase activity have been evaluated. The results showed that sapogenins can function as telomerase activators in MCF7 cell lines; however, they inhibit telomerase activity in HDF cells, suggesting that different extracts of *S. platensis* behave differently in different cell types [91].

Table2: anti-inflammatory effects of some herbal plants and their mechanism to mitigate inflammation

plant name	Active compound	Mechanism of anti-inflammatory effect	Disease/condition	Model organism	Ref.
<i>Rhodiola rosea</i>	Salidroside	↓ MAPK, NF-κB, JAK2/STAT3 and PI3K/PKB	ISO induced myocardial infarction(MI)	Rat	[92]
<i>Astragalus membranaceus</i>	Astragalus polysaccharide (APS)	↓ TNF-α, IL-1β and IL-6 ↓ MPO activity ↑ SOD Activity	ulcerative colitis	mice	[27]
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	triterpenoid saponins	↑ SMAD signaling pathway	Skin dryness	Healthy individuals	[93]
<i>Cistanche genus</i>	Echinacoside	↑ PKB/GSK3b pathway	epilepsy	Rats	[56]
<i>Panax ginseng</i>	Ginsenoside	↓ IL-6, IL-1β iNOS, and TNF-α	endometriosis	Rat	[94]
<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	fisetin and gallic acid	↓NO, TNF-α, IL-1β, and IL-6	lipopolysaccharide(LPS) stimulated macrophages	mouse	[95]
<i>Angelica sinensis</i>	oleic acid (OA)	↓ IL-1β, IL-6 and TNF-α	Alzheimer	mouse	[85]
<i>Spirulina platensis.</i>	Phycocyanin	↓ COX-2, TNF-α, and IL-6	rheumatoid arthritis and asthma	Rats	[90]
		↑ Tregs NK cells, CTLs	immunodeficiency	Human subjects	[96]
<i>Scutellaria baicalensis</i>	flavonoids baicalin, baicalein	↓ REV-ERBα ↑ BMAL1 expression ↑ MDA and MMP-1	Photoaging	UV-induced human dermal fibroblasts	[77]

MAPK: Mitogen-activated protein kinases; NF-κB: nuclear factor kappa light chain enhancer of activated B cells; JAK2/STAT3:Janus kinase 2/signal transducer and activator of transcription 3; PI3K:phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase; PKB: protein kinase B; TNF-α: Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha; , IL-1β :Interleukin-1 beta; IL-6:Interleukin 6; MPO: Myeloperoxidase; SOD: Superoxide Dismutase ; SMAD: Suppressor of Mothers against Decapentaplegic; GSK3b:glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta; iNOS: Inducible nitric oxide synthase; NO: nitric oxide; COX-2:cyclooxygenase-2; Tregs: T regulatory lymphocytes; NK cells: natural killer; CTLs: cytotoxic lymphocytes

Scutellaria baicalensis

Scutellaria baicalensis, a flowering plant in the Lamiaceae family, has long been used as herbal remedies for treating a wide range of disorders such as inflammatory, neurological, cardiovascular and cancer. *Scutellaria* species possess potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant flavonoids such as baicalin and baicalein, which have been evaluated in clinical trials. The application of *S. baicalensis* extract on the skin has been shown to counteract ROS, and demonstrate anti-aging effects. Baicalin's potent anti-senescence and anti-photoaging attributes were directly associated with its impact on SASP in both in vitro and in vivo models subjected to long-term UVB exposure, simulating skin photoaging. A 2023 study revealed that an extract derived from *S. baicalensis* exhibited anti-aging properties on human dermal fibroblasts by enhancing telomerase activity and decreasing oxidative stress[77]. A different research study explored the pharmacological impacts of (*Scutellaria baicalensis gorgi*) SBG on mice experiencing skin aging. This study revealed that SBG enhances telomerase activity and counteracts REV-ERB α , leading to an increase in BMAL1 expression and protection against the effects of skin aging. In a study assessing the protective effect of baicalin against UVA-induced dermal fibroblasts with decreased telomere length, an increase in MDA and MMP-1 levels was observed. The potential mechanisms through which baicalin functions as a protective agent against skin aging may involve the regulation of senescence-related genes and inhibition of oxidative damage[97].

Discussion

Skin aging is a natural process that occurs over time, but its visible effects can be a cause of concern for many individuals. Phytomedicine, which involves the use of herbal extracts in traditional medicine, has gained attention as a potential approach to address skin aging. Compared to chemical drugs, phytomedicine is believed to have fewer side effects, lower toxicity, and a reduced risk of adverse reactions.

One promising aspect of phytomedicine in the context of skin aging is the exploration of herbal telomerase activators. Telomeres are protective structures at the ends of chromosomes that shorten with each cell division, leading to cellular aging. Herbal extracts such as *Rhodiola rosea*, *Astragalus membranaceus*, *Centella asiatica*, the *Cistanche* Genus, *Panax ginseng*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Angelica sinensis* and *Scutellaria baicalensis* have shown potential in activating telomerase, an enzyme that can counteract telomere shortening. These botanical compounds influence telomerase activity through various mechanisms, including regulation of oxidative stress and key signaling pathways.

Oxidative stress is known to contribute to telomere shortening, and the antioxidant properties of herbal extracts can help mitigate this damage. Additionally, modulation of signaling pathways like MAPK and Akt may mediate the effects on telomerase activity. These botanical compounds not only neutralize oxidative stress but also have diverse impacts on cellular health, making them intriguing candidates for alleviating age-related telomere

shortening and inflammaging, which refers to chronic inflammation associated with aging.

One of the advantages of herbal extracts is their lower risk compared to chemical drugs. They are derived from natural resources and align with the body's natural processes. The bioactive compounds in herbal extracts can target different aspects of telomere maintenance, including telomerase activation, reduction of oxidative stress, modulation of inflammation, and support of cellular repair mechanisms. Moreover, the potential synergistic effects of different bioactive compounds in herbal extracts may enhance their overall efficacy. Plant extracts are also more readily accessible and available compared to chemical drugs.

However, it is crucial to address safety considerations and potential risks associated with the use of herbal telomerase activators. The delicate balance between enhancing cellular viability and unintentionally promoting abnormal cell proliferation must be carefully evaluated. Thorough preclinical and clinical investigations are necessary to assess the long-term safety profiles, potential interactions, and unexpected consequences of these herbal compounds. The effects of herbal compounds can vary across different cell types, emphasizing the need for comprehensive evaluations across a wide range of physiological systems.

Considering potential genotoxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity is critical, as any therapeutic approach involving the modulation of cellular processes must be approached with caution. Further research is needed to understand potential mechanistic links between telomerase activation and tumorigenesis and to address safety concerns associated with the use of these herbal extracts.

To translate the potential benefits of herbal extracts into clinical applications, rigorous frameworks and clinical trials are essential. These trials should evaluate the safety, efficacy, and long-term effects of interventions using herbal telomerase activators. It is important to consider the variability in individual responses, genetic predispositions, and other factors that can influence outcomes.

A deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying telomerase activation by botanical extracts is needed. Unraveling these mechanisms will facilitate the development of more targeted and effective therapeutics. While botanical extracts have the potential to enhance both longevity and quality of life in the aging population, it is important to approach remedies that affect telomere length with caution. The usage of botanical extracts for telomere lengthening should be implemented cautiously and under the supervision of experts to ensure the most beneficial effects while minimizing potential side effects.

In conclusion, the exploration of herbal telomerase activators in phytomedicine offers promise for addressing skin aging. However, further research is required to fully understand the mechanisms underlying telomerase activation and ensure its efficacy and safety as a therapeutic approach for age-related diseases.

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Ethical Approval Not applicable

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